

Comparative Study of the Solvent Effect on the Kinetics of Alkaline Hydrolysis of some Salicylates in Water-Acetone Medium

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Kinetic studies of alkaline hydrolysis of phenyl and ethyl salicylates have been done in aquo-acetone medium of varying composition (0–70% acetone, v/v) and varying temperatures (15–35°). Specific rate constant values have been found to decrease with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The activation parameters have been evaluated and variation of these parameters have been explained on the basis of solvent-solute interaction, solvation of the transition state and the dielectric behaviour of the medium.

STUDIES¹⁻⁸ regarding the effect of solvent on the alkaline hydrolysis of esters or amides are concerned with the recording and explanation for changes in rates of hydrolysis in binary solvent mixtures. Roberts^{7,8} supported the view of Parker⁹ which predicts rate enhancement in case of ester hydrolysis by dipolar aprotic solvent like acetone. However, other workers¹⁻⁶ found results which are not in line with that of Parker. They support the contention of Ingold¹⁰ and Laidler who predicted decrease in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. In few cases¹¹, Parker's view have been found to be operative in lower concentration region of the organic co-solvent but Ingold and Laidler's view has been found applicable in the higher concentration region of the organic co-solvent. Obviously more work is still to be done to establish the mechanism of solvation and effect of dielectric constant of the medium.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of AnalaR or C.P. (Merck) grade. Acetone was purified by standard method¹². The standard alkali and ester

solutions prepared in double-distilled water were thermostated separately in a water-bath ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) for 0.5 h, and the solutions were then mixed together. Aliquots (10 ml) of the reaction mixture withdrawn at definite intervals of time were poured into an ice-cold standard HCl solution (10 ml) and back-titrated with standard baryta solution. Reproducible results were obtained.

The specific rate constant values calculated in various solvent compositions and at different temperatures are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Results (Table 1) show that for both the esters specific rate constant values gradually decrease with increasing proportion of acetone at all the temperatures. The hydrolysis of the esters follows the B_{AC} mechanism, according to which addition of OH⁻ ions is the rate-determining step. The transition state, therefore, will be highly polar carrying two units of negative charge superimposed on it. The formation of such transition state must be favoured by increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Since acetone has lower dielectric constant

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANT ($k \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) OF ETHYL AND PHENYL SALICYLATES IN AQUOACETONE MEDIUM

Temp. °C	Ester	Acetone % (v/v)						
		10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%
15	Ethyl salicylate	9.3	7.4	5.9	4.4	3.8	3.0	2.5
	Phenyl salicylate	20.3	17.4	13.5	12.6	10.0	6.9	—
20	Ethyl salicylate	18.4	13.8	11.1	8.4	6.5	5.4	4.5
	Phenyl salicylate	36.9	33.1	25.5	23.4	19.9	15.7	10.8
25	Ethyl salicylate	35.4	26.0	19.3	15.1	11.8	9.4	7.6
	Phenyl salicylate	77.0	55.6	45.7	40.7	34.7	—	21.3
30	Ethyl salicylate	66.6	50.7	37.6	24.3	20.2	15.2	11.8
	Phenyl salicylate	125.9	104.7	91.2	83.8	69.2	60.3	54.4
35	Ethyl salicylate	115.5	93.0	67.1	46.2	32.5	26.8	21.3
	Phenyl salicylate	219.5	182.0	—	151.4	138.0	127.8	111.0

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than that of water, the bulk dielectric constant of the medium will gradually decrease with increasing proportion of acetone, thus disfavouring the formation of the transition state. Therefore, rate should fall with increasing proportion of acetone in the medium. This is what has been our observations in case of both the esters. Previous studies⁵⁻¹⁸ have also shown similar results.

A peculiar feature of variation has been noted by plotting $\log k$ values against mole percent of acetone (Figs. 1 and 2). At lower mole percent of acetone, the decrease in $\log k$ values for both the esters is sharp but they approach a limiting value in the region of 30–35 mole percent of acetone.

Activation energy: The activation energy value (E_0 ; Table 2) have been found to decrease steadily in case of both the esters with increasing volume percent of acetone. This trend in E_0 values indicates that either the transition state is more solvated than the initial state or the initial state is more desolvated as compared to the transition state.

Solvation phenomenon of this description should increase the rate with increasing percentage of acetone in the medium. But this does not happen because of the probable reason that the reaction is entropy-controlled. This view is in conformity with variation in ΔS^* value for both the esters which decreases with increasing acetone component in the reaction mixture (Table 2). Moreover, both

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k$ vs mole percent of acetone for alkaline hydrolysis of ethyl salicylate.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k$ vs mole percent of acetone for alkaline hydrolysis of phenyl salicylate.

the effects of dielectric factor and solvation are opposing the rate which probably accounts for a sharper decrease in $\log k$ values (Figs. 1 and 2) in the lower mole percent range of acetone.

Thermodynamic activation parameters: The thermodynamic activation parameters ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* were calculated by usual methods (Table 2).

The increase in ΔG^* though small with the increase in acetone proportion, is indicative of the specific desolvation of the transition state, supporting our view. Cleve¹⁴ and Elsemongy¹⁵ got similar observations.

Effect of ionic strength: The very small effect of ionic strength suggests that the reaction is ion-molecular type and not of ion-ion type.

Comparative study of specific rates of phenyl and ethyl salicylates: A comparison of rate values of ethyl and phenyl salicylates (Table 1) reveals that the value of k increases when ethyl group is substituted by phenyl group. Ethyl group being electron-donating, the slower rate of ethyl salicylate is quite justified. The enhancement in the rate due to phenyl group in the ester can be attributed to electron-attracting property of phenyl group. As regards the other aspects of rate data, they are quite similar.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF PHENYL AND ETHYL SALICYLATES IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITION OF AQUOACETONE MEDIUM

% of Acetone (v/v)	Phenyl salicylate				Ethyl salicylate			
	E_0 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹	E_0 kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
10	87.2	85.8	5.4	84.1	95.4	92.8	23.4	85.8
20	84.9	82.4	3.3	84.5	92.8	89.9	12.1	86.6
30	82.8	80.3	-9.6	84.9	89.9	87.9	0.8	87.0
40	79.9	78.2	-24.7	85.3	84.9	81.6	-19.1	87.9
50	77.8	76.1	-41.0	85.3	81.0	79.1	-31.4	88.3
60	75.7	74.9	-52.6	85.8	79.5	77.0	-40.2	89.1
70	73.2	72.8	-67.8	86.2	76.5	74.9	-49.4	89.5

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